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Building Information Modelling to Enhance Construction
Performance in Sri Lanka

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WARRANTY STATEMENT

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ABSTRACT

New mobile, wearable, and pervasive computing devices are growing increasingly practical and allowing people to access internet information anytime they want, wherever they are because computers getting more powerful and smaller. Building information modeling, or BIM, is an internet-based tool that is posing an issue to the construction industry by providing a platform for fully integrated design, modeling, asset preparation, and collaboration. AR systems integrate virtual information into the physical environment to give users the impression that it is all around them. BIM and AR work together to open up new avenues for architectural engagement, navigation, and visualization that transcend the limitations of fixed computer-based interaction and navigation. Mobile augmented reality (MAR) combines virtual objects created by computers with actual circumstances. Users of MAR systems can interact with MAR gadgets like smartphones and head-worn wearables and transition smoothly from the real world to a mixed reality environment that is full of digital objects. To provide free access to digital content, these MAR systems improve user interactions with MAR technology.

The main object of this study is to identify the most efficient AR integrated BIM techniques for enhancing Sri Lankan construction work performance. In this study, construction work performance is a dependent variable with the independent variable factors of accuracy and reliability, usability, cost effectiveness, flexibility and adaptability, safety and security, user acceptance and adoption, time and schedule, and quality. This quantitative study focused on the questionnaire and multiple regression research design to gather primary data in Sri Lanka by applying the survey method. The data was collected from 27 participants who were willing to participate. The results from the regression analysis have shown that Accuracy and Reliability, Cost Effectiveness and Quality are while Integrating AR with BIM positively affects the construction performance and that the results are significant. However, using AR in the construction sector is not without its difficulties. To effectively manage building projects employing AR applications in Sri Lanka's construction industry, several strategies must be put into use to address implementation challenges.

Keywords: BIM, Augmented Reality, Sri Lanka, Technology, Construction, Mobile Augmented Reality.

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TABLE OF CONTENTS

ABSTRACT.....	i
ACKNOWLEDGEMENT.....	ii
LIST OF FIGURES.....	v
LIST OF TABLES	vi
LIST OF APPENDICES.....	vi
LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS	vii
CHAPTER 1: INTRODUCTION.....	1
1.1: Research Background	1
1.2: Research Gap	2
1.3: Research Significance	2
1.4: Research Aim	2
1.5: Research Objectives.....	3
CHAPTER 2: LITERATURE REVIEW	4
2.1: Sri Lankan Construction Industry	4
2.2: BIM (Building Information Modeling).....	4
2.3: Mobile Augmented Reality	6
2.4: System Requirement	8
2.5: Information Collection from the Real-World	8
2.6: Information Flow from BIM Server to Mobile Device	9
2.7: The System Architecture of BIM ARSE (AR Service)	9
2.7.1: Object Detection and Data Visualization.....	9
2.7.2: De-featuring and Simplification of the BIM Model.	10
2.7.3: Low-latency Communication in Real-time Data Collection of Mobile/ IoT device	11
2.7.4: Workflow Management Synchronized with BIM.....	11
CHAPTER 3: METHODOLOGY	12
3.1 Research approach and data collection	12
3.2 Methodology	13
3.3: Analytical Model.....	15

3.4: Conceptual Framework.....	15
CHAPTER 4: ANALYSIS	17
4.1: Data Analysis.....	17
4.2: Descriptive Statistics.....	17
4.3: Demographic Data Analysis.....	19
4.3.1: Gender of Respondents	19
4.3.2: Age of Respondents	19
4.3.3: Education Level of Respondents.....	20
4.3.4: Employee Category.....	21
4.3.5: Occupation of Respondents	22
4.3.6: Years of Experience in BIM	23
4.4: Knowledge about the AR Technology	24
4.5: Construction Performance Analysis	28
CHAPTER 5: RESULTS.....	35
CHAPTER 6: DISCUSSION.....	38
CHAPTER 7: CONCLUSION	39
REFERENCES	42
APPENDIX.....	46

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 1: Sri Lanka GDP from Construction (ICRA Lanka, 2011).....	4
Figure 2: The system architecture of cyber-physical system for BIM AR service	10
Figure 3: Data processing and contents of cyber-physical system for BIM AR service	10
Figure 4: BIM activation for openMAINT.....	11
Figure 5: Flow of Methodology	15
Figure 6: Conceptual Framework	16
Figure 7: Gender of respondents, Source of survey (2023).....	19
Figure 8: Age of respondents, Source of survey (2023).....	20
Figure 9: Education level of respondents, Source of survey (2023).....	21
Figure 10: Employee category of respondents, Source of survey (2023).....	21
Figure 11: Occupation of respondents, Source of survey (2023)	22
Figure 12: Year of Experience of respondents, Source of survey (2023)	23
Figure 13: How familiar you with AR, Source of survey (2023)	24
Figure 14: Have you used AR technology in previous projects, Source of survey (2023)	24
Figure 15: How AR could be used to improve construction performance, Source of survey (2023)	25
Figure 16: Construction would benefit the most from AR integration, Survey of source (2023)	26
Figure 17: Challenges or limitations to using AR in the construction, Source of survey (2023)	27
Figure 18: Most important factors to consider when integrating AR, Source of survey (2023)	27

LIST OF TABLES

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics.....	18
Table 2: Gender of Respondents.....	19
Table 3: Age of respondents.....	20
Table 4: Education level of respondents.....	20
Table 5: Employee category of respondents.....	21
Table 6: Occupation of respondents.....	22
Table 7: Year of Experience of respondents.....	23
Table 8: Descriptive statistics in construction performance.....	28
Table 9: Correlations.....	30
Table 10: Model Summary.....	32
Table 11: ANOVA.....	33
Table 12: Coefficients.....	33

LIST OF APPENDICES

Appendix 1: Questionnaire Survey Form.....	46
Appendix 2: Activity Plan.....	54
Appendix 3: SPSS Outputs.....	55
Appendix 4: PPT3 & PPT4.....	60
Appendix 5: Log Book.....	61

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

1. BIM - Building Information Modelling
2. AR - Augmented Reality
3. ARSE – Augmented Reality Service
4. MAR - Mobile Augmented Reality
5. 3D – Three-Dimensional Scale
6. CAD - Computer-Aided-Design
7. KPI – Key Performance Indicators
8. AI – Artificial Intelligence
9. IOT - Internet of Things
10. QPMTF - Quality Performance Measurement Task Force
11. CII - Construction Industry Institute
12. EPC - engineer-procure-constructor.
13. QLASSIC - Quality Assessment System in Construction
14. AV - Augmented Virtuality
15. SPSS - Statistical Package for Social Sciences

CHAPTER 1: INTRODUCTION

1.1: Research Background

The modern building industry is rapidly moving in the direction of a method for a planned and sustainable construction process by applying new technologies that can enhance the construction performance of the construction system. According to the J. Ratajczak, M. Riedl and D. T. Matt (2019), the inability of construction stakeholders to effectively communicate construction-related information has been the most mentioned causes of weak performance in the construction industry throughout recent years. According to J. Wang, X. Wang, W. Shou, and B. Xu (2014) the focus of traditional methods for visualizing architectural drawings is stable pictures or three-dimensional (3D) scale models; but, these techniques have limitations, such as high prices for concept development, poor participants communication, limited ability to reuse. Building Information Modeling (BIM) and Applications for Augmented Reality (AR) are recommended to enhance construction performance.

The integration of both physical and digital data is the subject of one of the computer research areas known as augmented reality (AR), it is useful for having a better visualization style. According to Kalkofenetal (2009), the relationship between real and virtual objects when using AR as a visualization method is one of attentiveness and context: either giving a significant real-world challenge more variety among various settings or facilitating the user's ability to concentrate on an effective challenge that has been set on an actual basis. A. Javornik (2016) showed that Ivan Sutherland, the "father of computer graphics," a computer scientist, created an AR head-mounted device at Harvard University in 1968, which is credited with creating the foundational technology for augmented reality.

Building Information Modelling (BIM) is a method for designing, distributing, and maintaining data with all parties throughout the project lifecycle. According to J. Wang, X. Wang, W. Shou, and B. Xu (2014), the basis for digitization is the BIM method, which is based on 3D models. In the end, BIM is a platform for integrating many kinds of data into a single design as opposed to software. Construction procedures will probably soon include BIM.

Beyond the limitations of conventional fixed computer-based interaction and navigation, the blend of BIM and AR opens new possibilities for architectural visualization, navigation, and engagement. According to A. C. De Hugo Silva, M. Gaber, and M. Dolenc (2021) described that to visualize the purpose of building activities and goals, BIM can be used in combination with augmented reality (AR). With AR, activities and tasks may be displayed and analyzed in real-time, unlike BIM, which only offers stable and established data. This shows that the effectiveness of the construction process is a key problem to take into consideration as

decisions are made across every project, and that pinpointing the essential components or understanding how all these factors determine performance are relevant research topics.

1.2: Research Gap

It is correct to assert that augmented reality (AR) is not commonly used in Sri Lankan building maintenance methods. There isn't much research looking at how BIM (building information modeling) and AR (augmented reality) can be incorporated into the present visualization platforms to improve knowledge transfer and the productivity of the building industry. Because there hasn't been much research on augmented reality's capacity to improve Sri Lanka's building construction processes, there is a knowledge gap. Except for a few studies that are associated with the construction sector but do not specifically address the building industry's success in construction. Yet, no significant study has been performed to examine the use of AR in the building construction sector, especially in the Sri Lankan scenario. Keeping this in mind, the purpose of this research is to establish how augmented reality (AR) can be used to improve building performance in Sri Lanka during the maintenance stage.

1.3: Research Significance

As technology in our digital world develops, one trend that must be followed is augmented reality, which has recently been popular in the building industry. AR gives precise measures because it can measure a space's depth, height, and width. Additionally, by recognizing problems and finding solutions to them to minimize the need for rework, AR enables on-site adjustments. On large construction sites, paper-based documentation such as plans, construction logs, and sketches are still used for information management. Making informed decisions is difficult in this situation since it frequently results in misunderstandings between participants, faulty construction, and an incomplete knowledge of the current situation. The likelihood of errors on construction sites is increased by incomplete or erroneous information, which can result in a decline in built environment quality. The purpose of this research is to assess Sri Lanka's performance in terms of timeliness, quality, safety, and user experience in order to identify the best AR-integrated BIM approaches for enhancing the country's building activity.

1.4: Research Aim

The goal of this study is to determine the most effective AR integrated BIM techniques for enhancing Sri Lankan construction work performance.

1.5: Research Objectives

Building information modeling (BIM) is growing more commonly employed in the construction industry, however, its applicability outside of the design process is still in its infancy. Another possibility is an AR-improved BIM modeler, in which BIM model data is modified in an AR environment. The following findings are expected from this investigation.

- To conduct a review of the literature to determine how this technology is currently being used in the construction industry and how it may be applied to enhance construction performance.
- To recognize what factors to measure construction work performance in Sri Lanka.
- Create a survey questionnaire and gather information based on those construction performance measuring variables.
- Provide relevant AR integration suggestions for the Sri Lankan construction industry.

CHAPTER 2: LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1: Sri Lankan Construction Industry

The construction industry is crucial to Sri Lanka's economy. The construction sector creates both small-scale infrastructure like highways, power plants, and petrochemical complexes as well as large-scale infrastructure like individual residences. As a result of the country's post-conflict situation, the building sector in Sri Lanka is expanding. The island's ethnic conflict eventually ended in 2009, reviving economic activity and sparking an increase in infrastructural construction. Significant reconstruction work is expected in the north and east of the country. It is projected that there would be significant development in the other regions of the nation as well. (ICRA Lanka, 2011).

Figure 1: Sri Lanka GDP from Construction (ICRA Lanka, 2011)

2.2: BIM (Building Information Modeling)

CHAI et al. (2019) said that BIM is seen as a developing innovation that can, at its most basic, improve project delivery. Different technologies must be integrated with effective management practices and strategies for BIM. This is considered important in reducing the number of BIM issues. As a result, various forms of management and project organization are needed to promote the various rates of BIM adoption and precocity. According to M Poljansek (2017) described that much of the reduction in construction productivity is brought on by information issues, whether they are brought on by weak commercial interfaces, communication failures in the supply chain, or ineffective labor processes. Individual project team members cannot

provide the best outcome in the most efficient way if they do not have timely access to accurate, complete, and reliable information.

H. Penttila (2006) studied Building information modeling (BIM) is a collection of related practices, methodologies, and technology innovations that offer "a methodology for handling all the required building design, performance, and project information in digital layout across the building's life cycle." Because there is no relationship between the actual and virtual worlds in building information modeling, it may be difficult to completely interpret digital project information.

According to M Poljansek (2017) in his study, He demonstrated how BIM, or building information modeling, is an amazing technological advancement that is entirely integrating design, modeling, resource planning, and communication. It provides the prospect for significant efficiency gains by providing all parties with a digital depiction of a building's attributes during its entire existence. Although BIM was originally designed for construction projects, its benefits, such as less rework, fewer errors, integration, and design data that may eventually be utilized to support operations, maintenance, and quality management, have made it a viable alternative for other types of projects as well. According to J.E. Taylor, and P.G. Bernstein (2009) explained to develop and represent a facility, BIM can begin with parametric 3D CAD tools and techniques. Additionally, the dimensions may be in 4D or 5D, with 4D incorporating a time dimension and 5D including time-based expenditures. Information sharing between project stakeholders has been a problem for the construction industry over time, which is one of the main causes of failure.

2.3: Building Performance Measurement

T. Roshana and A. Akintoye (2002) analyze the performance parameters developed to measure the success of the project and outline a method for assessing the performance of the stakeholders engaged in the construction. According to Cox (2003) determined that establishing appropriate key performance indicators (KPIs) that are most important in measuring the overall success of firm building projects is the first step in measuring company performance and utilizing the benchmarking approach. Key performance indicators are collections of data measurements used to evaluate the effectiveness of a construction project. D.S. Santoso and P. G. M. P. Gallage (2019) in their study showed there are 9 internal and 1 external aspect listed as important elements. Seven of these had to do with contractors, suggesting that they play a bigger part in measuring performance. The parties' lack of managerial and technical abilities, human capacity, awareness of and understanding of the surrounding environment, as significant contributors to the basic features, political activity and changes in governmental policy were noted.

Shaneet al. (2009) cost performance is influenced by aspects from both the internal and external areas. Both elements in this group that the project participants directly control and those that they do not are included. While scope, complexity, cost, and time performance are examples of internal variables, macroeconomic conditions, political influences, and environmental concerns are examples of external variables. Volden (2018) and Flyvbjerg (2007) accepted that achieving the goals of schedule, cost, and quality required accountability and ongoing evaluation of the efforts. Locatelli et (2017) and Dissanayaka and Kumaraswamy (1999) suggested that the cost and timeline of the project, the performance of the project team, the project's environment and characteristics, the amount of funding contributed, outside variables, the project's design and technology aspects, and the qualifications and connections of the contractor, client, and consultants are several factors that affect a project's efficiency.

2.3: Mobile Augmented Reality

According to Y. Zhou, H. Luo, Y. Yang (2017) shows that Complex and high-tech construction sites are increasingly dependent on the integration of Building Information Modeling (BIM) with the Internet of Things (IoT), Augmented Reality (AR), and Artificial Intelligence (AI). However, A. Fazel, A. Izadi (2018) determined a low-cost cyber-physical system that integrates BIM with IoT and AR is required since these technologies may be too expensive and inaccessible for small enterprises with limited resources. A few BIMS systems coupled with AR systems have been used in numerous construction-related industries. To solve the cost issue, a low-cost mobile AR system for BIM was designed and tested for pipe repair. Y. Zhou, H. Luo, Y. Yang (2017) shows that Future research should concentrate on creating low-cost digital systems that incorporate BIM, IoT, AR, and AI to enhance maintenance, visualization, and decision assistance in on-site operations while being affordable for businesses with tight budgets. It costs money to install devices, develop software, and educate employees when deploying an augmented reality system architecture. However, the IT industry is helping the AR software community grow, and this pattern is projected to drive down development costs in the future.

According to G. Ellis (2022) the term "construction quality" refers to projects that are completed within the constraints established by the Scope of Work. Finishing the project on time, meeting the parameters of the agreement, and staying under budget are all critical aspects of quality management. Nudurupati, S., Arshad, T., Turner, T., showed that (2007) A causal relationship between the factors influencing quality performance was established, demonstrating that improved project management actions, the effectiveness of the team leader, the viability and feasibility of procedures, and the stability of the project environment can all lead to an increase in client satisfaction with quality. The Construction Industry Institute (CII) Quality Performance Measurement Task Force (QPMTF) blueprint for measuring quality performance on engineer-

procure-construct (EPC) projects in the United States (Glagola et al., 1992; Stevens, 1996); and the Quality Assessment System in Construction (QLASSIC) model developed by Chan (2001) are three models for measuring construction project quality.

According to Kwon et al. (2014) determined that a prior study on reinforcing concrete intended to improve the manual-based fault system by merging mobile AR technologies, BIM, and image-matching. They proposed a process based on two flawed systems. First, an image-matching system to enable off-site quality inspection. Second, a mobile AR application that allows workers or site managers to detect dimension problems and omissions on the project site automatically. An experiment to examine the suggested system demonstrated the system's effectiveness, which can be applied to other applications. In tunneling construction Zhou et al., (2017) investigate the capacity of AR technology to detect segment movement by supplementing the quality inspector's ability to pull QC digital models into the workspace.

S. Liam (2022) Using augmented reality technology, the physical properties of a space, such as its height, width, and depth, may be measured. Construction companies can use this data to create models, allowing them to create more realistic buildings and get a complete picture of how the project will look. Having precise measurements in advance allows for more accurate material and labor estimates, as well as a more efficient project timeline. Yuen et al. (2011) showed that AR has emerged to the construction progress monitoring by the merging of actual and virtual items, interactive in real time, and registering the virtual imagery with the real environment. Milgram et al. (1995) More specifically, Augmented Virtuality (AV), which takes the real world and real environments as its background and in which a computer-generated world serves as the background while real-world data is merged in and superimposed. (Milgram, et al., 1995).

2.4: System Requirement

J. Um, J. M. Park, S. Y. Park, G. Yilmaz, (2023) the authors of the reviewed paper examined the requirements of a Building Information Modelling-Augmented Reality (BIM-AR) system to improve interoperability and automate data handling based on previous use cases. The authors conducted a user requirements analysis to assess both usability and implementation challenges. The review analyzed the use cases of BIM applications and 5G-based BIM AR services, where the Internet of Things (IoT) framework is mainly used for building smart city solutions. Furthermore, AI and AR systems that employ BIM have been developed for maintenance and monitoring.

The use case analysis in terms of function automation and interoperability, was presented in M.H. Stoltz, V. Giannikas, D. McFarlane, J. Strachan, J. Um, R. Srinivasan (2017) and M. Ruskowski (2018) determined that the authors As the key needs of the proposed service, the importance of automated service and compatibility was underlined. Furthermore, the authors defined needs for improving specific components of the previously developed systems. They concluded that addressing interoperability and automated data handling challenges is crucial for the successful implementation of BIM-AR systems.

J. Um, J. M. Park, S. Y. Park, G. Yilmaz, (2023) described that Design consideration #1 highlights the importance of showing data to AR devices, which requires automatic data conversion and shape extraction functions. The need for automation in sensor signal updating and automatic pre-processing and recognition is emphasized for efficient data handling. Interoperability is also crucial and can be achieved through a standardized data model and open software. The paper linked the automation and interoperability needs to the BIM-AR system's components, giving a helpful reference for further investigation. The literature provides valuable insights into developing a BIM-AR system capable of handling massive BIM data, enabling automation and interoperability, and improving the system's effectiveness.

2.5: Information Collection from the Real-World

Jumyung Um, Joung min Park, Seo yeon Park, Gokcen Yilmaz (2023) showed the integration of BIM and IoT technologies in the AEC/FM industry is a crucial topic of discussion, and this paper presents valuable insights into it. The authors have proposed design considerations that could serve as an important reference for further development and analysis of BIM-IoT systems. Emphasizing automation and interoperability, the authors have stressed utilizing optimized IoT infrastructure and facility models to create an efficient system capable of real-time big data analytics.

2.6: Information Flow from BIM Server to Mobile Device

The main objective of the research conducted by the authors is to address the problem of latency in BIM applications incorporating AR technology. J. Um, J. M. Park, S. Y. Park, G. Yilmaz, (2023) the authors propose a solution that utilizes a high-speed 5G network and a chain of Mobile-Edge-Cloud connections to reduce latency and provide on-site workers with a real-time, high-resolution AR service. The authors argue that real-time response times are crucial in BIM applications, as construction workers require rapid decision-making capabilities. However, boosting data transmission speeds for video streaming or solid modeling data utilized in an AR service is limited by the current network system. To achieve quicker data transfer speeds and prevent delay difficulties, the authors propose balancing the computing load of each service deployed in the Mobile-Edge-Cloud chain. The study provides a promising solution to the latency issues faced by construction workers when using BIM applications with AR technology, and the proposed use of a high-speed 5G network and the Mobile-Edge-Cloud chain is expected to improve data transfer speeds and provide a high-quality AR service for on-site users.

2.7: The System Architecture of BIM ARSE (AR Service)

J. Um, J. M. Park, S. Y. Park, G. Yilmaz, (2023) showed that this literature examines architecture that seeks to achieve this objective. Its purpose is towards creating a self-sustaining information exchange system that operates within a closed-loop network. This system functions by collecting data from IoT sensors and transmitting it between AR smart glasses and the BIM system. A graphical representation of its operation is presented in **Figure 2**.

2.7.1: Object Detection and Data Visualization

J. Um, J. M. Park, S. Y. Park, G. Yilmaz, (2023) The authors highlighted the obstacles of merging AR with BIM and provided strategies to solve them, such as employing geometric deep learning for object recognition and establishing a low-latency AR service on a mobile-edge platform. The paper emphasized the importance of real-time response in AR services and presented a comparative analysis to support this claim. The proposed solutions can lead to an improved AR experience for users.

2.7.2: De-featuring and Simplification of the BIM Model.

In summary, the challenges that arise when using BIM data in AR applications and propose numerous methods for reducing data size and computing load, thereby improving the performance of AR systems. These techniques include de-featuring functions, surface model conversion, and simplification algorithms. The proposed system combines data handling standards and achieves object selection through de-featuring changes. Data processing and content conversion from BIM to AR data are illustrated in **Figure 3**, which provides a clear visual representation of the system.

Figure 2: The system architecture of cyber-physical system for BIM AR service

Figure 3: Data processing and contents of cyber-physical system for BIM AR service

2.7.3: Low-latency Communication in Real-time Data Collection of Mobile/ IoT device

The BIM AR-SE system manages large sensor data volumes from mobile/IoT devices with improved approaches at the IoT edge and in the database level. Using a 5G network, video streaming improves communication and latency between Mobile, BIM, and AR devices. Performance is evaluated with test services in IoT/Edge/Cloud and video streaming is wirelessly transferred. J Um, V Gezer, A Wagner, M Ruskowsk (2019) evaluated the system's performance was evaluated using various Wi-Fi connections in the mobile-edge, and the connection quality was assessed using the edge device and cloud server.

2.7.4: Workflow Management Synchronized with BIM.

Tecnoteca srl (2020) described that to make this possible, a setup involving Ubuntu 20.04, Git, OpenJDK 11, Docker, and Docker Compose was established. Furthermore, conurbation synchronization between the two systems occurs automatically using the IFC open standard format. Upon local deployment of the BIM server application, a connection was established between it and Open MAINT Figure 4. By doing so, users can conveniently access the 3D models in Open MAINT and initiate maintenance activities for various model components. This accessibility also enables the tracking of maintenance chores from various places such as technical offices and on-site operations.

Figure 4: BIM activation for openMAINT

CHAPTER 3: METHODOLOGY

This chapter on research methodology explains in full the framework and procedures employed to conduct a questionnaire survey and gather information in agreement with those construction performance assessment variables. This chapter covers the research methodologies that were employed in the study, including the collection of quantitative data from respondents. It also focuses on the research design and a sample population case study.

3.1 Research approach and data collection

Burns and Grove (2005) explained that According to the type of study, a variety of research design are categorized, including case study, survey, and experimental designs. This study used quantitative research because it is a rigorous, objective, systematic approach of gathering information that uses numerical data. The object of this study is to identify the variables that determine construction work efficiency in Sri Lanka and to suggest appropriate AR integration techniques that could be applied there. This was quantitative research. The method of quantitative analysis includes data and numbers, most of which are seen in figures. A descriptive survey design was used in this investigation. The participants in this questionnaire survey were chosen from among BIM experts, technical officers, construction managers, safety officers, draftsmen, civil engineers, architects, and project managers. The parameters used to measure construction performance and apply AR-BIM technology are the basis for each question in this questionnaire. According to those questions, the questionnaire respondents' agreement is evaluated. This study will mostly apply descriptive and exploratory research, which will be centered on the research challenges, questions, and aims.

The questionnaire served as the strategic point for the research because a questionnaire is where a survey is conducted, and because a questionnaire is where AR technology was used by BIM practitioners, technical officers, construction managers, safety officers, draftsmen, civil engineers, architects, and project managers, those respondents provided answers to questions via survey. These eight indicators are taken into consideration when creating the survey questions. The questionnaire was created with the goal of gathering data from the sample population to understand how to measure construction work performance in Sri Lanka, how to employ AR technology, and how important the aspects are to the sector. A quantitative approach was used to examine the data, and IBM SPSS statistics version 25 was mainly utilized for this purpose.

BIM practitioners, technical officers, construction managers, safety officers, draftsmen, civil engineers, architects, and project managers in Sri Lanka represent the population of this study. The sampling size is a factor that is considered while choosing the sample size. A convenience

sampling technique (random sampling) was applied to select a sample of 27 respondents, among whom include a BIM practitioner, technical officers, construction managers, safety officers, draftsmen, civil engineers, architects, and project managers. 27 of the 27 questionnaires issued to the sample population received responses, making the response rate overall 100%.

The two primary types of research methodologies are qualitative and quantitative. While qualitative research relies on verbally describing an event, quantitative research relies on statistics and numbers that are often presented in figures. This investigation was carried out using quantitative research methodology. Kotler (2000) determined in his research that in addition to surveys, experiments, group-focused attention, and observation, four instruments should be employed to gather data and information from primary sources. However, this study used surveys to gather the responses to these questions and conducted numerous in-person interviews. Kawamala (2013) defined that Questionnaires are simple to use, somewhat quick to gather data, and less costly than other methods. The information was gathered through a questionnaire-based survey.

3.2 Methodology

To determine how to quantify the performance of construction work in Sri Lanka, utilization of AR technology, and the importance of the factors in the construction sector, a questionnaire was created with the goal of gathering data from the sample population. A guaranteed in the surveys that the information gathered through their responses would be kept secure and confidential. In addition, the questionnaire had a few closed questions regarding topics that respondents were required to provide information on. These questions were spread among respondents to gather both qualitative and quantitative information about Sri Lanka's active building sites.

Section one of the questionnaires for this study comprised demographic information in six questions covering gender, age, education level, employee category, occupation, and years of BIM experience. In the second part, questions about how experienced in augmented reality technology and how it might be applied to the building industry in Sri Lanka were also asked. And the third part is about construction performance. The study comprised 24 basic questions about construction performance and employed a 5-point Likert scale in section three, with a level starting from 1 to 5 indicating a significant disagreement. However, the terminology employed in the questionnaire is straightforward in order for respondents to understand them when answering questions. There are various benefits to using the questionnaire: Responders can fill out all questions completely and relax; the answers are completely confidential because

there is no name or signature; and the author can utilize surveys in places where he or she cannot reach using a new approach such as Google docs or email.

To gather pertinent information, a simple random probability sampling was chosen. The study decided who to include as a respondent for the questions that would be produced to gather data, and it had a greater chance to choose the appropriate respondents by using these sampling procedures. The convenience sampling method was used to choose the BIM with AR user sample for this study. The sampling size is a factor that is considered while choosing the sample size. Nevertheless, the sample size for this study was 27 out of 27 randomly chosen respondents.

The Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) software was used to collect and code information from the field via the questionnaires that were distributed. Frequencies, means, and reliability were primarily determined using SPSS to evaluate data from the questionnaire, and content validity was established by evaluating past study results. Computer-based software for data analysis, interpretation, and evaluation. The study presents the research's conclusions based on the data that were gathered. Using the program IBM SPSS statistics version 25, graphs, charts, and other graphical representations have been utilized to present data in an intelligible way. Additionally, IBM SPSS Statistic version 25 was used to perform a descriptive analysis on the information gathered by the questioner.

To examine data, the Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) was typically utilized. The demographic or bio data were examined using descriptive data analysis. Frequency distribution and percentages are among the statistics computed. For each of the relevant variables, the statistics evaluated comprised frequency distributions and percentages. Multiple regression analysis is performed in the second phase of the technique for this study to test the findings. Construction performance is chosen as the dependent variable, and BIM with AR indicators are chosen as the independent variables. The model explains the connection between Accuracy and Reliability, Usability, Cost Effectiveness, Flexibility and Adaptability, Safety and Security, User Acceptance and Adoption, Time and Schedule, and Quality of Construction Performance. Multiple regression, correlation, analysis of variance, and linear regression were the main methods. Multiple regression analysis was used to evaluate the conceptual framework or model, and the results were compared to the demographic attributes of the respondents using analysis of variance. The current percentage of respondents who are now utilizing technology and their satisfaction levels are displayed in pie charts, bar charts, and column charts.

Figure 5: Flow of Methodology

3.3: Analytical Model

$$\text{Construction Performance} = \alpha + \beta_1 \times (\text{Accuracy and reliability}) + \beta_2 \times (\text{Ease of Use}) + \beta_3 \times (\text{Cost effectiveness}) + \beta_4 \times (\text{Flexibility and adaptability}) + \beta_5 \times (\text{Safety and security}) + \beta_6 \times (\text{User acceptance and adoption}) + \beta_7 \times (\text{Time and schedule}) + \beta_8 \times (\text{Quality})$$

3.4: Conceptual Framework

There is a relationship between the dependent variable (construction performance) and the independent variable (BIM with AR) in the model, which is included and explained here, as well as the hypothesis in this study.

H1: Integrating AR with BIM positively affects the performance indicator of Accuracy and reliability.

H2: Integrating AR with BIM positively affects the performance indicator of Ease of Use.

H3: Integrating AR with BIM positively affects the performance indicator of Cost effectiveness.

H4: Integrating AR with BIM positively affects the performance indicator of Flexibility and adaptability.

H5: Integrating AR with BIM positively affects the performance indicator of Safety and security.

H6: Integrating AR with BIM positively affects the performance indicator of User acceptance and adoption.

H7: Integrating AR with BIM positively affects the performance indicator of Time and schedule.

H8: Integrating AR with BIM positively affects the performance indicator of Quality.

Figure 6: Conceptual Framework

CHAPTER 4: ANALYSIS

4.1: Data Analysis

This chapter includes a complete explanation of the study as well as an analysis of the data in accordance with the specified objectives, which are to find the optimal methods of AR integrated BIM to improve construction work performance in Sri Lanka. The surveys in this study were separated into three sections: demographics, AR technology knowledge, and construction performance. Analyze section one to obtain valid data from the respondents' personal information in this area. To evaluate the hypothesis model, all acquired data will be analyzed using SPSS software in this chapter. A 5-point Likert scale methodology was used to organize the data. This is used to evaluate the participants' responses. SPSS is used to evaluate numerical data quantitatively. The questionnaire evaluates the major variables of the study, and structured close-ended questionnaires with a 5-point Likert scale ranging from strongly disagree to strongly agree are to be used for this research work to answer the research questions, and it is used to measure the responses of this study's respondents.. First, descriptive statistics will be used for the study's demographic data and relevant questions concerning the building industry. Second, this study used multiple regression analysis (inferential statistics) to assess the study's suggested model.

4.2: Descriptive Statistics

Descriptive statistics are frequently used to analyze the central trend of a dataset. The mean, median, mode, and dispersion (variability) tend to estimate where data falls, and the variance and its square root examine how data spreads out. The standard deviation of the data demonstrated the data's dispersion from its mean. This methodological approach involves using a questionnaire to determine the appropriate methods of AR integrated BIM to improve construction work performance in Sri Lanka, as well as determining what factors to measure construction work performance in Sri Lanka and suggesting suitable AR integration methods that we can use in the Sri Lankan construction industry. The distributed questionnaire was completed by 27 people. The questionnaire responses were received from various groups in Sri Lanka. Simple, straightforward, and closed-ended questions were posed to them.

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics

Descriptive Statistics					
	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Gender	27	1	2	1.37	.492
Education Level	27	2	4	2.59	.694
Age	27	1	5	2.30	.993
Employment Category	27	1	2	1.41	.501
Occupation	27	1	8	3.89	2.455
Years of experience in BIM	27	1	4	1.81	.962

4.3: Demographic Data Analysis

4.3.1: Gender of Respondents

Table 2 shows the gender results from the survey, which show that the majority of the sample 16 respondents are Males 59 percent and 11 respondents are Females. Figure 7 shows that male respondents are more probable to work in the construction industry than female respondents.

Table 2: Gender of Respondents

Gender of Respondents	Frequency	Percentage
Male	16	59.0
Female	11	41.0
Total	27	100.0

Figure 7: Gender of respondents, Source of survey (2023)

4.3.2: Age of Respondents

The results are obtained in table 3 and figure 8 also the maximum age of respondents between 26-35 years with 52 percent, after between 36-45 years is a second highest with 22 percent, also 15 percent related to 25 years or below as a third highest, therefore, 4 percent has been filled related to Above 55 years as lowest amount respondents that answered.

Table 3: Age of respondents

Age	Frequency	Percentage
25 years or below	4	15
26-35 years	14	52
36-45 years	6	22
46-55 years	2	7.
Above 55 years	1	4

Figure 8: Age of respondents, Source of survey (2023)

4.3.3: Education Level of Respondents

The results are shown in table 4 and figure 9, with the majority of respondents having a diploma 48 percent and the second level of respondents having completed a bachelor's degree 41 percent, and the least amount of respondents having a master's degree 11 percent. According to the findings of their study, users of AR technology in the construction business in Sri Lanka have varying levels of education.

Table 4: Education level of respondents

Education Level	Frequency	Percentage
Diploma Course	13	48
Bachelor's Degree	11	41
Master's Degree	3	11

Figure 9: Education level of respondents, Source of survey (2023)

4.3.4: Employee Category

Related to the Employee Category of Respondents, most respondents are employed in the private sector with 59 percent and the lowest level are doing government sector with the rate of 41 percent, the result has been shown in table 5 and figure 10.

Table 5: Employee category of respondents

Employee Category	Frequency	Percentage
Private Sector	16	59
Government Sector	11	41

Figure 10: Employee category of respondents, Source of survey (2023)

4.3.5: Occupation of Respondents

Related to the Occupation of Respondents, most respondents are employed as Technical Officer by 22 percent and the second highest are employed as Civil Engineer with the rate of 26 percent and rate of 19 percent are employed as Draftsman, and the lowest level have other professions that, Project Manager, Construction Manager, Architecture and Safety Officer as mentioned with 7 percent, the result has been shown in table 6 and figure 11.

Table 6: Occupation of respondents

Occupation	Frequency	Percentage
Technical Officer	6	22
Draftsman	5	19
BIM Practitioner	2	8
Project Manager	1	4
Construction Manager	2	7
Civil Engineer	7	26
Architecture	2	7
Safety Officer	2	7

Figure 11: Occupation of respondents, Source of survey (2023)

4.3.6: Years of Experience in BIM

The aim of to know years of experience in BIM those who are working in Sri Lanka, the result shown in the table 7 and figure 12 that most respondents who have 1-3 years with rate of 48 percent, and the second highest respondents who have 4-6 years with rate of 30 percent, and in the end and lowest respondents who have 10-12 years with the rate 7 percent.

Table 7: Year of Experience of respondents

Years of experience BIM	Frequency	Percentage
1-3 years	13	48
4-6 years	8	30
7-9 years	4	15
10-12 years	2	7

Figure 12: Year of Experience of respondents, Source of survey (2023)

4.4: Knowledge about the AR Technology

How familiar are you with AR technology and its potential uses in construction?

The results obtained in figure 13 show that 82 percent of respondents are somewhat familiar and 11 percent respondents are not familiar with AR technology. 7 percent of respondents are Very familiar with AR technology.

Figure 13: How familiar you with AR, Source of survey (2023)

Have you used AR technology in any of your previous construction projects?

The results obtained in figure 14 shown that 96.3 percent respondents have not used AR technology in previous construction projects and only one percent respondent has used AR technology in previous construction projects.

Figure 14: Have you used AR technology in previous projects, Source of survey (2023)

How do you think AR technology could be used to improve construction work performance in Sri Lanka?

Related to the how do you think AR technology could be used to improve construction work performance, the majority of respondents are in by providing real-time information on construction progress with 52 percent and the second highest are in by improving communication and collaboration among project stakeholders with the rate of 30 percent and the lowest are in by enhancing safety on construction sites with 19 percent, the result has been shown in figure 15.

Figure 15: How AR could be used to improve construction performance, Source of survey (2023)

Which areas of construction would benefit the most from AR technology integration?

Related to which areas of construction would benefit the most from AR technology integration of respondents, most respondents are 13 in Design and planning with 48 percent and the second highest are 6 in Quality control and inspection with 22 percent and the lowest are 3 in training and education with 11 percent, the result has been shown in figure 16.

Figure 16: Construction would benefit the most from AR integration, Survey of source (2023)

Any potential challenges or limitations to using AR technology in the construction industry in Sri Lanka?

The results are obtained in figure 17 which factors do you consider when using the AR technology in construction industry, majority of respondents are thought that have potential challenges or limitations to using AR technology with the 96 percent and the lowest of respondents are thought that haven't potential challenges or limitations to using AR technology with a rate of 4 percent.

Figure 17: Challenges or limitations to using AR in the construction, Source of survey (2023)

What do you think would be the most important factors to consider when implementing AR technology in construction projects in Sri Lanka?

Related to the most important factors to consider when implementing AR technology, most respondents thought that cost and availability of hardware and software with 48 percent and the second highest of respondents thought that Integration with existing processes and technologies with the rate of 33 percent and the lowest of respondents thought that Training and support for users with 19 percent, the result has been shown in figure 18.

Figure 18: Most important factors to consider when integrating AR, Source of survey (2023)

4.5: Construction Performance Analysis

Multiple regression was chosen as the model to determine the best AR integrated BIM solutions for improving construction job performance in Sri Lanka. Multiple regression analysis provides an unbiased way of identifying the type and extent of the link between independent and dependent variables. (Sekaran & Bougie, 2010; Field, 2009). Construction performance is chosen as the dependent variable in the third section of this study's analysis, while indications of the use of BIM with AR are chosen as the independent variables. The model describes the relationship between Accuracy and reliability, Ease of Use, Cost effectiveness, Flexibility and adaptability, Safety and security, User acceptance and adoption, Time, and schedule, and Quality over construction performance. Determine the descriptive statistics (mean and standard deviations) for each dimension in the first phase. Then, determine whether or not each indication is associated with the others using correlation analysis. The association between the factors and construction performance is then examined for significance level using multiple regression analysis. The 5-point Likert scale is analyzed using the mean approach. And the potential model for this analysis is shown below

Analytical Model

Construction Performance = $\alpha + \beta_1 \times (\text{Accuracy and reliability}) + \beta_2 \times (\text{Ease of Use}) + \beta_3 \times (\text{Cost effectiveness}) + \beta_4 \times (\text{Flexibility and adaptability}) + \beta_5 \times (\text{Safety and security}) + \beta_6 \times (\text{User acceptance and adoption}) + \beta_7 \times (\text{Time and schedule}) + \beta_8 \times (\text{Quality})$

Table 8: Descriptive statistics in construction performance

Descriptive Statistics			
	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Construction Performance	4.0511	.72060	27
Accuracy and Reliability	4.0389	.71245	27
Ease of Use	3.4348	.53709	27
Cost Effectiveness	3.4226	.67706	27
Flexibility and Adaptability	3.5204	.50043	27
Safety and Security	4.0504	.63785	27
User Acceptance and Adoption	3.6196	.49642	27

Time and Schedule	3.7178	.61104	27
Quality	3.9522	.72012	27

The description provided in Table 8 indicates that the mean of reliability and accuracy is 4.038 with a standard deviation of 0.712. The mean score of ease of use is 3.434, with a standard deviation of 0.537. The mean cost-effectiveness value is 3.422, with a standard deviation of 0.677. The mean score of flexibility and adaptability is 3.520, with a standard deviation of 0.500. The mean score for safety and security is 4.050, with a standard deviation of 0.637. The mean score for user acceptance and adoption is 3.6196, with a standard deviation of 0.496. The mean score for time and schedule is 3.717, with a standard deviation of 0.611. Finally, the mean quality score is 3.952 with a standard deviation of 0.720.

Pearson correlation is a statistical test used to figure out the relationship between variables, and Table 9 below shows the relationship between construction performance and independent variables, as well as the correlation level to significance, which is 0.01 (1-tailed), and based on the below results, there is a relationship of correlation, firstly between construction performance and Accuracy and Reliability is 0.311, and it is a weak positive correlation. The difference between construction performance and ease of use is 0.218, indicating a weak positive association. The correlation coefficient between construction performance and cost-effectiveness is 0.475, indicating a weak positive association. The association between construction performance and flexibility and adaptability is (-0.014), which is a very small negative correlation. The difference between construction performance and Safety and Security is 0.701 and it is a positive strong correlation. The difference between construction performance and User Acceptance and Adoption is (-0.304) and it is a weak negative correlation. The difference between construction performance and Time and Schedule is 0.607 and it is a strong positive correlation. Lastly, the difference between construction performance and Quality is 0.565 and it is positive strong correlation.

Table 9: Correlations

Correlations									
	Con. Performance	Accuracy and Reliability	Ease of Use	Cost Effectiveness	Flexibility and Adaptability	Safety and Security	User Acceptance and Adoption	Time and Schedule	Quality
Construction Performance	1	.311	.218	.475	-.014	.701	-.304	.607	.565
Accuracy and Reliability	.311	1	-.153	-.253	-.020	.136	.274	.104	.371
Ease of Use	.218	-.153	1	.278	.391	.221	.152	.296	.044
Cost Effectiveness	.475	-.253	.278	1	.039	.327	.012	.442	.360
Flexibility and Adaptability	-.014	-.020	.391	.039	1	-.164	.178	.179	.075
Safety and Security	.701	.136	.221	.327	-.164	1	-.37	.301	.340
User Acceptance and Adoption	-.304	.274	.152	.012	.178	-.370	1	.079	-.007

	Time and Schedule	0.607	0.104	0.296	0.442	0.179	0.301	0.079	1	0.432
	Quality	.565	.371	.044	.360	.075	.340	-.007	.432	1
Sig. (1-tailed)	Construction Performance	.	.057	.137	.006	.473	0	.061	0	.001
	Accuracy and Reliability	.057	.	.223	.101	.461	.249	.083	.303	.028
	Ease of Use	.137	.223	.	.080	.022	.134	.225	.067	.413
	Cost Effectiveness	.006	.101	.080	.	.424	.048	.475	.010	.033
	Flexibility and Adaptability	.473	.461	.022	.424	.	.206	.188	.186	.355
	Safety and Security	0	.249	.134	.048	.206	.	.029	.064	.041
	User Acceptance and Adoption	.061	.083	.225	.475	.188	.029	.	.348	.487
	Time and Schedule	0	.303	.067	.010	.186	.064	.348	.	.012
	Quality	.001	.028	.413	.033	.355	.041	.487	.012	.

The correlation coefficient of 1 (sig 0.01) indicates that there is also an important and positive association between construction performance and construction performance, as shown in Table 9. As a result, recognize that construction performance has a large and positive influence on construction performance.

According to table 10, the R square value is (0.822), which means that almost 82 percent of construction performance (dependent) is determined by the eight dimensions (independent variables). The adjusted R square value is (0.743), which means that after adjusting all variables, nearly 74 percent of construction performance (dependent) is determined by the eight dimensions (independent variables), and the value of adjusted R square is (0.743).

Table 10: Model Summary

Model Summary ^b									
R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics					Durbin-Watson
				R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change	
.907 ^a	.822	.743	.36547	.822	10.385	8	18	.000	2.279
a. Predictors: (Constant), Quality, User Acceptance and Adoption, Ease of Use, Flexibility and Adaptability, Cost Effectiveness, Time and Schedule, Safety and Security, Accuracy and Reliability									
b. Dependent Variable: Construction Performance									

Table 11 shows the results of the ANOVA analysis and whether or not there is a statistically significant difference between the dependent and independent variables. As shown, the significance value is 0.000, which is less than 0.05. As a result, there is a statistically significant difference between construction performance and independent variables.

Table 11: ANOVA

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	11.097	8	1.387	10.385	.000 ^b
	Residual	2.404	18	.134		
	Total	13.501	26			
a. Dependent Variable: Construction Performance						
b. Predictors: (Constant), Quality, User Acceptance and Adoption, Ease of Use, Flexibility and Adaptability, Cost Effectiveness, Time and Schedule, Safety and Security, Accuracy and Reliability						

Table 12: Coefficients

Coefficients								
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	95.0% Confidence Interval for B	
		B	Std. Error				Beta	Lower Bound
		1	(Constant)	-0.144	1.02		-.141	0.889
Accuracy and Reliability	.405		.140	.401	.899	.010	.112	.699
Ease of Use	.128		.168	.095	.762	.456	-.225	.480
Cost Effectiveness	.316		.145	.297	2.185	.042	.012	.620
Flexibility and Adaptability	-.014		.166	-.010	-.084	.934	-.363	.335
Safety and Security	.31		.156	.275	.992	.062	-.017	.638

	User Acceptance and Adoption	-.514	.185	-.354	-.772	.083	-.904	-.124
	Time and Schedule	.380	.145	.322	2.623	.077	.076	.684
	Quality	.070	.132	.070	.534	.034	-.207	.347
a. Dependent Variable: Construction Performance								

Construction Performance = (- 0.144) + 0.405 (Accuracy and reliability) +0.128 (Ease of Use) +0.316 (Cost effectiveness) + (-0.014) (Flexibility and adaptability) + 0.310 (Safety and security) + (-0.514) (User acceptance and adoption) + 0.380 (Time and schedule) + 0.070 (Quality)

Table 12 shows the findings of the regression analysis, which reveal that Accuracy and Reliability, Cost Effectiveness, and Quality have a positive association with the most successful AR-integrated BIM approaches for enhancing construction work in Sri Lanka, and that the results are significant. Therefore, the null hypotheses are ruled out. And all other factors are insignificant. Table 12 shows that the P value or significant result is 0.010, 0.042, and 0.034, which means that the P value is less than the 0.05 level of significant and should be rejected. According to the data obtained from respondents, integrating AR with BIM positively affects the performance indicators of accuracy and reliability, cost effectiveness, and quality.

CHAPTER 5: RESULTS

H1: Integrating AR with BIM positively affects the performance indicator of accuracy and reliability.

The results from the regression analysis have shown in the table that accuracy and reliability have a positive relationship with most effective AR-integrated BIM methods for improving the construction performance and that the results are significant. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected.

$$B = 0.405$$

$$P = 0.010 < 0.05 \text{ (significant)}$$

H2: Integrating AR with BIM positively affects the performance indicator of ease of use.

The results from the regression analysis have shown in table that ease of use hasn't a positive relationship with most effective AR-integrated BIM methods for improving the construction performance and that the results are not significant. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted.

$$B = 0.128$$

$$P = 0.456 > 0.05 \text{ (not significant)}$$

H3: Integrating AR with BIM positively affects the performance indicator of cost effectiveness.

The results from the regression analysis have shown in table that cost effectiveness has a positive relationship with most effective AR-integrated BIM methods for improving the construction performance and that the results are significant. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected.

$$B = 0.316$$

$$P = 0.042 < 0.05 \text{ (significant)}$$

H4: Integrating AR with BIM positively affects the performance indicator of Flexibility and Adaptability.

The results from the regression analysis have shown in table that of Flexibility and Adaptability hasn't a positive relationship with most effective AR-integrated BIM methods for improving the construction performance and that the results are not significant. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted.

$$B = -0.014$$

$$P = 0.934 > 0.05 \text{ (not significant)}$$

H5: Integrating AR with BIM positively affects the performance indicator of Safety and Security.

The results from the regression analysis have shown in table that of Safety and Security hasn't a positive relationship with most effective AR-integrated BIM methods for improving the construction performance and that the results are not significant. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted.

$$B = 0.310$$

$$P = 0.062 > 0.05 \text{ (not significant)}$$

H6: Integrating AR with BIM positively affects the performance indicator of User Acceptance and Adoption.

The results from the regression analysis have shown in table that User Acceptance and Adoption hasn't a positive relationship with most effective AR-integrated BIM methods for improving the construction performance and that the results are not significant. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted.

$$B = (-0.514)$$

$$P = 0.083 > 0.05 \text{ (not significant)}$$

H7: Integrating AR with BIM positively affects the performance indicator of Time and Schedule

The results from the regression analysis have shown in table Time and Schedule hasn't a positive relationship with most effective AR-integrated BIM methods for improving the construction performance and that the results are not significant. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted.

$$B = 0.380$$

$$P = 0.077 > 0.05 \text{ (not significant)}$$

H8: Integrating AR with BIM positively affects the performance indicator of accuracy and reliability.

The results from the regression analysis have shown in the table that accuracy and reliability have a positive relationship with most effective AR-integrated BIM methods for improving the construction performance and that the results are significant. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected.

$$B = 0.070$$

$$P = 0.034 < 0.05 \text{ (significant)}$$

CHAPTER 6: DISCUSSION

The results of this study point to finding the best AR-integrated BIM techniques for improving Sri Lanka's construction industry's productivity. Construction performance was measured using three distinct questions that were chosen from eight different aspects of the independent variable BIM with AR by 24 questions. The demographic analysis shows that more males 59 percent answered for this questionnaire. The majority in the questionnaire age is between 26-35 years old by 60 percent, Also the diploma course has a majority by 48 percent for education level, in the employee category the majority of responders has gotten private sector by 59 percent, However, the civil engineers have in first ranking with 26 percent, and last question the majority of respondent's year of experience is 1-3 years and with rate of 48 percent. However, finding from the regression estimation the Integrating AR with BIM positively affects the construction performance as presume from the questions at the beginning of the research. The findings from Pearson correlation and explore show a positive and strong correlation between dependent and Accuracy and Reliability, Cost Effectiveness and Quality independent variables and statistically significant. The results from the regression analysis have shown that Accuracy and Reliability, Cost Effectiveness and Quality are while Integrating AR with BIM positively affects the construction performance and that the results are significant. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected. And other all factors are not significant.

CHAPTER 7: CONCLUSION

Today, a lot of construction organizations have a corporate mission that prioritizes the needs of the consumers and employees. The findings showed that three indicators accuracy and reliability, cost effectiveness, and quality were important from the workers' point of view. The discipline of facilities management, particularly in connection to building maintenance, adopts AR is a revolutionary idea with wide applications to streamline processes. A solution is suggested to handle these problems using augmented reality and a building information model, and it has the potential to result in cost and time reductions as well as high customer satisfaction and high profitability. The development of a facility Information Model for an existing facility and training the technicians to use a new system, however, may present difficulties. Through this study, it is suggested that further investigation be made into the causes and problems that frontline maintenance technicians encounter that lead to ineffective maintenance practices, as well as the potential applications of cutting-edge ideas like building information modeling, the internet of things, and augmented reality in Sri Lanka.

One of the biggest obstacles to adopting AR with BIM in the construction sector is a lack of expertise in software and technology. As a result, new technologies like AR may not be adopted readily by the construction's various stakeholders. Due to their "unwillingness to change" mentality, individuals are more likely to adopt traditional construction methods than revolutionary technologies. And also can demonstrate how society has adapted more to technological advancements in daily tasks. The adoption of new technologies by those working in the construction business, however, consistently falls short of expectations. Most of the respondents cited "cost" as a key obstacle to AR adaption in the Sri Lankan setting. The "higher tax concessions" offered by the government have a direct bearing on the increased upfront cost of buying the hardware and software needed for AR implementation with BIM in Sri Lanka's building sector. In particular, the use of some AR-related hardware, such as smart headphones and smartphones, might lead to health and safety concerns on building sites. In addition, this will cause health difficulties such issues with the eyes and ears. Another significant obstacle to deploying AR in the Sri Lankan construction industry is "lack of accuracy and reliability." To reduce handling challenges while using AR on construction sites, a portable device should be used.

To prevent the problem of insufficient precision and reliability, it is possible to suggest "implementing AR for the little construction project" at the starting step. As a result, it would enable professionals in the construction sector to conduct adequate testing ahead and look for potential technical advancement to the AR applications in large-scale construction projects. The difficulty of inadequate knowledge of software and hardware and unfamiliarity with new

technologies must be overcome by modernizing the educational system of the nation by "integrating AR techniques to the university education." More "academic contribution to the research and growth" of augmented reality (AR) and its practical implications in the Sri Lankan construction industry, as well as "conducting workshops and training programs" at the organizational level on AR implementation, would also help to address the problem of construction professionals' lack of familiarity with new technologies, fill knowledge gaps regarding AR practices, and get past their resistance to adopting new practices.

As a result, actions will be taken to reduce health and safety concerns regarding the implementation of AR in Sri Lanka, including limiting and monitoring data access, "implementing a proper user guideline," and training professionals and workers in the construction industry to adhere to proper site safety procedures to reduce on-site accidents, as well as "taking precautions to reduce health issues" that can arise due to negligence while handling the hardware related to AR immobilization. In addition, the respondents have suggested a number of approaches to deal with the challenges of implementing AR in the Sri Lankan construction industry, such as holding workshops and training sessions, carrying out procedures for research and development, and instructing industry professionals through university education.

Apart from construction and assembly, additional manufacturing processes that might gain a lot from the use of mobile augmented reality system technologies are inspection and maintenance. Augmented reality can enhance collaboration in remote work contexts by enabling teams to exchange 3D visuals and videos with team members who aren't nearby. Stakeholders may view images or videos in more detail with the use of augmented reality, enabling them to spot errors or issues without actually being in the structure. With augmented reality, project progress may be tracked and documented. A range of technologies are available in the market to help construction professionals monitor the development of their projects. These apps detect you in the floor plan and start automated photo taking at each capture place using the augmented reality capabilities of your device. Accuracy and efficiency of progress capture are increased by ensuring that team members continually capture at the same location throughout time.

This connection enables natural interaction with the user, creating engagement within the BIM models, to speed up response time about possible answers for re-fitting activities at the construction site. Due to improvements in the performance of portable computers, mobile devices, and other solutions for visualization devices in a actual world, the potential application of the integration between BIM and AR increases. Techniques for tracking pictures have become popular, including visual (fiduciary) markers and positional sensors like GPS for

information and guidance. Due largely to these technologies' low cost, simplicity of use, and widespread adoption. The performance of smartphones, mobile computers, and devices with included accelerometers, gyroscopes, and external sensors has been improved as part of investments to popularize augmented reality. As a recommendation for future study, it is important to look into how AR affects how work is performed in terms of its quality, speed of execution, reduction of losses, and boost in worker productivity. In particular, mobile augmented reality techniques are recommended for BIM. A BIM and AR integration model must be created to validate the integration's promising potential.

However, using AR in the construction sector is not without its difficulties. Therefore, the object of this study was to find the difficulties in integrating AR and possible solutions in the Sri Lankan construction sector. To successfully complete construction projects using AR apps, a number of methods must be implemented in order to overcome the AR implementation challenges in the Sri Lankan construction industry.

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APPENDIX

Appendix 1: Questionnaire Survey Form

Integrating Augmented Reality (AR) with Building Information Modelling (BIM) to enhance Construction work Performance in Sri Lanka

Dear respondent,

I am an undergraduate student of Department of Civil Engineering, Kingston University London. As a partial requirement of the degree, I am conducting a research to evaluate the Integrating Augmented Reality (AR) with Building Information Modelling (BIM) to enhance Construction work Performance in Sri Lanka. The information gathered by this survey will only be used for the above purpose and your answers will be treated with almost confidentiality. Your valuable time and commitment extended to respond to this survey will be highly appreciated.

Thank You.

Yours Sincerely,

D.M.K.G. Manukularathna

kaveenhedu@gmail.com

Section A – Demographic Characteristics

- | | | | | | |
|-----------|---|--------------------------|-------------------|--------------------------|--------|
| 1. Gender | - | <input type="checkbox"/> | male | <input type="checkbox"/> | female |
| 2. Age | - | | 25 years or below | <input type="checkbox"/> | |
| | | | 26-35 years | <input type="checkbox"/> | |
| | | | 36-45 years | <input type="checkbox"/> | |
| | | | 46-55 years | <input type="checkbox"/> | |
| | | | Above 55 years | <input type="checkbox"/> | |

3. Educational Level-	No formal education	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Diploma course	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Bachelor's degree	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Master's degree	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Higher degree	<input type="checkbox"/>
4. Form of employment -	Private sector	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Government sector	<input type="checkbox"/>
5. Occupation-	Technical officer	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Draftsman	<input type="checkbox"/>
	BIM practitioner	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Project manager	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Construction manager	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Civil engineer	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Architecture	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Safety officer	<input type="checkbox"/>
6. experience in BIM-	1-3 years	<input type="checkbox"/>
	4-6 years	<input type="checkbox"/>
	7-9 years	<input type="checkbox"/>
	10-12 years	<input type="checkbox"/>
	13-15 years	<input type="checkbox"/>
	More than 15 years	<input type="checkbox"/>

Section – B

1. How familiar are you with AR technology and its potential uses in construction?

- a. Very familiar
- b. Somewhat familiar
- c. Not familiar

2. Have you used AR technology in any of your previous construction projects?

- a. Yes
- b. No

3. How do you think AR technology could be used to improve construction work performance in Sri Lanka?

- A. By providing real-time information on construction progress
- B. By improving communication and collaboration among project stakeholders
- C. By enhancing safety on construction sites

4. In your opinion, which areas of construction would benefit the most from AR technology integration?

- a. Design and planning
- b. Quality control and inspection
- c. Training and education
- d. Safety and Security

5. How do you think AR technology could be integrated with BIM to enhance construction work performance in Sri Lanka?

- a. By providing real-time updates on BIM models
- b. By allowing for remote collaboration on BIM models
- c. By enabling on-site visualization of BIM models

6. Do you think there are any potential challenges or limitations to using AR technology in the construction industry in Sri Lanka?

- a. Yes
- b. No

7. How do you think AR technology could be used to improve safety on construction sites in Sri Lanka?

- a. By providing real-time information on potential hazards
- b. By enabling remote monitoring of construction activities
- c. By providing access to safety instructions and procedures

8. What do you think would be the most important factors to consider when implementing AR technology in construction projects in Sri Lanka?

- a. Cost and availability of hardware and software
- b. Training and support for users
- c. Integration with existing processes and technologies.

9. How do you think AR technology could improve communication and collaboration among construction project stakeholders in Sri Lanka?

- a. By providing real-time access to project information
- b. By allowing for remote collaboration on project documents
- c. By enabling on-site visualization of project plans

10. In your opinion, what is the potential for AR technology to drive innovation and productivity in the construction industry in Sri Lanka?

- a. High potential
- b. Moderate potential
- c. Low potential

Section – C

Using a rating scale from the lowest point of 1 to the highest point of 5, please select the number that indicates your level of agreement or disagreement with the following statements.

SD = Strongly Disagree **D**= Disagree **N**= Neutral

A= Agree **SA**= Strongly Agree

<u>Accuracy and reliability</u>	SD	D	N	A	SA
To what extent do you agree with the statement: "I had confidence in the accuracy and reliability of the AR and BIM system."					
To what extent do you agree with the statement: "I think the AR and BIM system to be a useful tool for identifying and addressing potential issues or problems during construction."					
From what you know, do you believe that AR integration with BIM can be an accurate and reliable tool for accessing and using building information?					

<u>Ease of Use</u>	SD	D	N	A	SA
To what extent do you agree with the statement: "I am confident in my ability to use BIM and AR technology in construction projects"					
To what extent do you agree with the statement: "BIM and AR technology could be useful for training and education in the construction industry"					
To what extent do you agree with the statement: "I believe that BIM and AR technology will become widely used in the Sri Lankan construction industry"					

<u>Cost effectiveness</u>	SD	D	N	A	SA
To what extent do you agree with the statement: "BIM and AR technology could help to reduce costs and increase efficiency in construction projects".					
To what extent do you agree that the integration of AR with BIM has helped to improve the safety and productivity of construction workers, leading to cost savings on construction projects in Sri Lanka?					
To what extent do you agree with the statement: "BIM and AR technology provides a good return on investment in the construction industry:"					

<u>Flexibility and adaptability</u>	SD	D	N	A	SA
To what extent do you agree with the statement: "BIM and AR technology are an effective way for construction firms to become more adaptable and flexible".					
To what extent do you agree with the statement: "BIM and AR technology make it easy to adjust to unexpected changes during construction projects".					
To what extent do you agree with the statement: "BIM and AR technology enable construction firms to be more flexible with their resources".					

<u>Safety and security</u>	SD	D	N	A	SA
To what extent do you agree with the statement: "BIM and AR technology could improve safety on construction sites"					
To what extent do you agree with the statement: "I believe that BIM and AR technology have improved safety standards in the construction industry".					
To what extent do you agree with the statement: "BIM and AR technology can improve the overall security of the construction industry"					

<u>User acceptance and adoption</u>	SD	D	N	A	SA
To what extent do you agree with the statement: "BIM and AR technology could improve communication and collaboration among team members in construction projects"					
To what extent do you agree with the statement: "I am interested in using BIM and AR technology in my future construction projects"					
To what extent do you agree with the statement: "by using AR with BIM, users can gain a deeper understanding of the information and how it relates to the physical environment."					

<u>Time and schedule</u>	SD	D	N	A	SA
To what extent do you agree with the statement: "BIM and AR technology will help improve time management"					
In your opinion, do you think that AR integration with BIM can help avoid delays or setbacks during the construction process?					
From what you know, do you believe that AR integration with BIM can be an effective tool for staying on schedule during the construction process?					

<u>Quality</u>	SD	D	N	A	SA
To what extent do you agree with the statement: "BIM and AR technology could improve the quality of construction work"					
In your opinion, do you think that AR integration with BIM can help ensure that the finished building or construction project meets all quality and performance standards?					
Based on your understanding, do you think that AR integration with BIM can make it easier for construction professionals to identify and resolve issues or discrepancies, leading to a higher quality construction process?					

Appendix 3: SPSS Outputs

Descriptive Statistics						
	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation	
Gender	27	1	2	1.37	.492	
Education Level	27	2	4	2.59	.694	
Age	27	1	5	2.30	.993	
Employment Category	27	1	2	1.41	.501	
Occupation	27	1	8	3.89	2.455	
Years of experience in BIM	27	1	4	1.81	.962	
Valid N (listwise)	27					

Statistics							
		Gender	Age	Education Level	Employment Category	Occupation	Years of experience in BIM
N	Valid	27	27	27	27	27	27
	Missing	0	0	0	0	0	0
Mean		1.37	2.30	2.59	1.41	3.89	1.81
Mode		1	2	2	1	1	1
Std. Deviation		.492	.993	.694	.501	2.455	.962
Minimum		1	1	2	1	1	1
Maximum		2	5	4	2	8	4

Gender					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Male	17	63.0	63.0	63.0
	Female	10	37.0	37.0	100.0
	Total	27	100.0	100.0	

Age					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	25 years or below	5	18.5	18.5	18.5
	26-35 years	13	48.1	48.1	66.7
	36-45 years	6	22.2	22.2	88.9
	46-55 years	2	7.4	7.4	96.3
	Above 55 years	1	3.7	3.7	100.0
	Total	27	100.0	100.0	

Education Level					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Diploma Course	14	51.9	51.9	51.9
	Bachelor's Degree	10	37.0	37.0	88.9
	Master's Degree	3	11.1	11.1	100.0
	Total	27	100.0	100.0	

Employment Category					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Private Sector	16	59.3	59.3	59.3
	Government Sector	11	40.7	40.7	100.0
	Total	27	100.0	100.0	

Occupation					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Technical Officer	7	25.9	25.9	25.9
	Draftsman	4	14.8	14.8	40.7
	BIM Practitioner	2	7.4	7.4	48.1
	Project Manager	2	7.4	7.4	55.6
	Construction Manager	2	7.4	7.4	63.0
	Civil Engineer	6	22.2	22.2	85.2
	Architecture	2	7.4	7.4	92.6
	Safety Officer	2	7.4	7.4	100.0
	Total	27	100.0	100.0	

Years of experience in BIM					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1-3 years	13	48.1	48.1	48.1
	4-6 years	8	29.6	29.6	77.8
	7-9 years	4	14.8	14.8	92.6
	10-12 years	2	7.4	7.4	100.0
	Total	27	100.0	100.0	

Descriptive Statistics			
	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Construction Performance	4.0511	.72060	27
Accuracy and Reliability	4.0389	.71245	27
Ease of Use	3.4348	.53709	27
Cost Effectiveness	3.4226	.67706	27
Flexibility and Adaptability	3.5204	.50043	27
Safety and Security	4.0504	.63785	27
User Acceptance and Adoption	3.6196	.49642	27
Time and Schedule	3.7178	.61104	27
Quality	3.9522	.72012	27

Model Summary ^b										
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	R Square Change	Change Statistics			Sig. F Change	Durbin-Watson
						F Change	df1	df2		
1	.907 ^a	.822	.743	.36547	.822	10.385	8	18	.000	2.279

a. Predictors: (Constant), Quality, User Acceptance and Adoption, Ease of Use, Flexibility and Adaptability, Cost Effectiveness, Time and Schedule, Safety and Security, Accuracy and Reliability

b. Dependent Variable: Construction Performance

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	11.097	8	1.387	10.385	.000 ^b
	Residual	2.404	18	.134		
	Total	13.501	26			

a. Dependent Variable: Construction Performance

b. Predictors: (Constant), Quality, User Acceptance and Adoption, Ease of Use, Flexibility and Adaptability, Cost Effectiveness, Time and Schedule, Safety and Security, Accuracy and Reliability

Correlations

		Construction Performance	Accuracy and Reliability	Ease of Use	Cost Effectiveness	Flexibility and Adaptability	Safety and Security	User Acceptance and Adoption	Time and Schedule	Quality
Pearson Correlation	Construction Performance	1.000	.311	.218	.475	-.014	.701	-.304	.607	.565
	Accuracy and Reliability	.311	1.000	-.153	-.253	-.020	.136	.274	.104	.371
	Ease of Use	.218	-.153	1.000	.278	.391	.221	.152	.296	.044
	Cost Effectiveness	.475	-.253	.278	1.000	.039	.327	.012	.442	.360
	Flexibility and Adaptability	-.014	-.020	.391	.039	1.000	-.164	.178	.179	.075
	Safety and Security	.701	.136	.221	.327	-.164	1.000	-.370	.301	.340
	User Acceptance and Adoption	-.304	.274	.152	.012	.178	-.370	1.000	.079	-.007
	Time and Schedule	.607	.104	.296	.442	.179	.301	.079	1.000	.432
	Quality	.565	.371	.044	.360	.075	.340	-.007	.432	1.000
Sig. (1-tailed)	Construction Performance	.	.057	.137	.006	.473	.000	.061	.000	.001
	Accuracy and Reliability	.057	.	.223	.101	.461	.249	.083	.303	.028
	Ease of Use	.137	.223	.	.080	.022	.134	.225	.067	.413
	Cost Effectiveness	.006	.101	.080	.	.424	.048	.475	.010	.033
	Flexibility and Adaptability	.473	.461	.022	.424	.	.206	.188	.186	.355
	Safety and Security	.000	.249	.134	.048	.206	.	.029	.064	.041
	User Acceptance and Adoption	.061	.083	.225	.475	.188	.029	.	.348	.487

Coefficients ^a								
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	95.0% Confidence Interval for B	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1	(Constant)	-.144	1.020		-.141	.889	-2.288	2.000
	Accuracy and Reliability	.405	.140	.401	2.899	.010	.112	.699
	Ease of Use	.128	.168	.095	.762	.456	-.225	.480
	Cost Effectiveness	.316	.145	.297	2.185	.042	.012	.620
	Flexibility and Adaptability	-.014	.166	-.010	-.084	.934	-.363	.335
	Safety and Security	.310	.156	.275	1.992	.062	-.017	.638
	User Acceptance and Adoption	-.514	.185	-.354	-2.772	.013	-.904	-.124
	Time and Schedule	.380	.145	.322	2.623	.017	.076	.684
	Quality	.070	.132	.070	.534	.600	-.207	.347

a. Dependent Variable: Construction Performance

Residuals Statistics ^a					
	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Predicted Value	2.1634	5.0495	4.0511	.65329	27
Std. Predicted Value	-2.890	1.528	.000	1.000	27
Standard Error of Predicted Value	.121	.296	.207	.044	27
Adjusted Predicted Value	2.3688	5.0669	4.0645	.65426	27
Residual	-.56107	.65404	.00000	.30409	27
Std. Residual	-1.535	1.790	.000	.832	27
Stud. Residual	-1.980	1.896	-.017	1.001	27
Deleted Residual	-.93342	.74962	-.01339	.44779	27
Stud. Deleted Residual	-2.176	2.059	-.018	1.042	27
Mahal. Distance	1.868	16.146	7.704	3.626	27
Cook's Distance	.000	.289	.053	.068	27
Centered Leverage Value	.072	.621	.296	.139	27

a. Dependent Variable: Construction Performance

Appendix 4: PPT3 & PPT4

My Research Progress

1. Literature review

- Still in progress but, critical construction performance measurement factors are identified which need to consider when making the questionnaire.

2. Questioner survey (BIM Practitioners in Sri Lanka)

- Questionnaire form was finished

Consist with 3 parts

1. Section A (demographic characteristics)
2. Section B (About the Knowledge of AR technology)
3. Section C (Construction performance)

- Still have gathered 6 responses

PPT3

Occupation
6 responses

- Technical Officer
- Draftsman
- BIM Practitioner
- Civil Engineer
- Architecture
- Safety Officer
- Construction Manager
- Project Manager

How do you think AR technology could be used to improve construction work performance in Sri Lanka?
6 responses

- By providing real-time information on construction progress
- By improving communication and collaboration among project stakeholders
- By enhancing safety on construction sites

What do you think would be the most important factors to consider when implementing AR technology in construction projects in Sri Lanka?
6 responses

- Cost and availability of hardware and software
- Training and support for users
- Integration with existing processes and technologies

Some responses gathered in Section B

Construction Performance

SD D N A SA

Questionnaire Results (Section C)

PPT4

Appendix 5: Log Book

INFORMATION OF THE STUDENT

Student Name : D.M.K.G. Manukularathna.....

Contact Phone Number : 0716722983.....

Research Title : Integrating Augmented Reality (AR) with Building Information
Modelling (BIM) to Enhance Construction Work Performance in
Sri Lanka.....

Name of Supervisor : Ms. Tharika Kahandawa.....

ESOFT Reg Number : KTB/A-002068.....

KU Reg Number : K2277970.....

Supervisor Meeting No.....01.....

Date :.....12/11/2022.....

Time :...8.00pm.....

Supervisors Comments

Student Comments

In the first day session, Ms. Tharika taught us what are the contents should be in the interim report, how the content should be organized and how to write each of content.

Things to be completed before next meeting by student

- Prepare a simple document including Aim, Objectives and Methodology of the research.

.....
Signature of Student

.....
Signature of Supervisor

.....
Signature of Co-Supervisor

Supervisor Meeting No.....02.....

Date :.....19/11/2022.....

Time :...8.00am.....

Supervisors Comments

Student Comments

In the second day session, I presented a simple presentation to Ms. Tharika including the Aim, Objectives, and Methodology of my research. there were some minor points that I need to consider in my research methodology. after changing those points Ms. Tharika says that I'm ok to move forward.

Things to be completed before next meeting by student

- Present the progress of interim report writing.

.....
Signature of Student

.....
Signature of Supervisor

.....
Signature of Co-Supervisor

Supervisor Meeting No.....03.....

Date :...26/11/2022.....

Time :...7.00pm.....

Supervisors Comments

The student was well prepared and had a good understanding of his methodology. He was advised to continue with his literature review and report.

Student Comments

In the 3rd day session, the progress of my research was discussed and I was instructed to send the introduction and literature review part of my research to Ms. Tharika before the next session.

Things to be completed before next meeting by student

- Complete the introduction and literature review part.

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Signature of Student

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Signature of Supervisor

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Signature of Co-Supervisor

Supervisor Meeting No.....04.....

Date :...03/12/2022.....

Time :...7.00pm.....

Supervisors Comments

The student has done a good job overall. Minor comments were addressed.

Student Comments

In the 4rd day session, the progress of my research was discussed and I was instructed to send a draft report of my Interim report to Ms. Tharika.

Things to be completed before next meeting by student

- Complete the Interim report and submit.

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Signature of Student

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Signature of Supervisor

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Signature of Co-Supervisor

Supervisor Meeting No.....05.....

Date :...17/12/2022.....

Time :...11.30am.....

Supervisors Comments

Madam Tharika said that the questionnaire form should be completed by next week.

Student Comments

On the fifth day session, Madam Tharika taught us how to collect data for our research projects. In my case, I'm using a questionnaire survey.

Things to be completed before next meeting by student

- Complete the questionnaire form

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Signature of Student

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Signature of Supervisor

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Signature of Co-Supervisor

Supervisor Meeting No.....06.....

Date :...07/01/2023.....

Time :...10.30am.....

Supervisors Comments

Madam Tharika asked me to initiate the data collection process.

Student Comments

During the session on the fifth day, Madam Tharika remarked that my questionnaire form appeared to be well-designed and thoughtfully arranged.

Things to be completed before next meeting by student

- Initiate the data collection process

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Signature of Student

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Signature of Supervisor

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Signature of Co-Supervisor

Supervisor Meeting No.....08.....

Date :...04/02/2023.....

Time :...11.30am.....

Supervisors Comments

- According to Madam Tharika, the number of responses I had collected at that point was too low, and she advised me to aim for at least 25 responses.
- Madam Tharika said to complete the final presentation and send it to her before submitting.

Student Comments

- I have collected only 10 responses by then. I was instructed to collect at least 25 responses.

Things to be completed before next meeting by student

- Collect 25 responses at least.
- Complete the final presentation

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Signature of Student

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Signature of Supervisor

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Signature of Co-Supervisor

Supervisor Meeting No.....09.....

Date :...11/03/2023.....

Time :...5.30am to 9.00am...

Supervisors Comments

- Ms. Tharika and Ms. Dilrangi commented that my presentation slides had been well arranged.
- According to the comments that I received, the people who filled out the survey form should have experience in BIM.

Student Comments

Things to be completed before next meeting by student

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Signature of Student

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Signature of Supervisor

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Signature of Co-Supervisor

Supervisor Meeting No.....10.....

Date :...18/03/2023.....

Time :.....6.00am.....

Supervisors Comments
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Ms. Tharika gave instructions on what content should be included in the analysis section.
Student Comments
Things to be completed before next meeting by student

- Completing the data analysis part of my research.

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Signature of Student

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Signature of Supervisor

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Signature of Co-Supervisor